

Geopolitics and GIS: Lincolnshire and Yorkshire during the Reign of King Stephen, c. 1135 – 1154

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Biography:

Ryan Prescott is currently undertaking his PhD on the civil war conflict between Stephen and Matilda and its alleged impact on the fortified monuments of the twelfth century, including castles, elite residences and religious buildings. He also has an interest in how technology can improve archaeological research.

Summary

The reign of King Stephen, 1135-54, has long been condemned as a period of anarchy and chroniclers and historians have readily linked the emergence of unlicensed castles to its troubles. The twelfth century has typically been studied using documentary sources, but an archaeological survey is still lacking. With the use of a geographical information system, this paper provides a greater insight into how the built environment was used and experienced. Though the region hosted the defining battles of the period, the archaeology indicates that the conflict between Stephen and Matilda did not have such a detrimental effect on its landscape.

KEYWORDS: up to 5 keywords or short phrases relevant to the work
Middle Ages, Archaeology, Interdisciplinary, Challenging Preconceptions

1.1 Introduction

The reign of King Stephen, 1135-54, has long been condemned as a period of anarchy, which allegedly saw a widespread breakdown in the societal and cultural norms of England. Chroniclers and historians alike have viewed the actions of his magnates as a symptom of this and have readily linked the emergence of countless so-called adulterine fortifications to its troubles. More recent studies have started to revise this view, but an overall archaeological survey, or its presentation in GIS, of the civil war period is still lacking. For the most part, its buildings are still viewed within this narrow framework and are not recognised for representing anything other than what their present day remains suggest. The apparent simplicity in the designs of these buildings, the predominant use of timber and relative haste in which monuments appeared and disappeared in their landscapes, is often seen as evidence for its instability.

1.2 Overview

Writers from the period have defined the nineteen year conflict as having impacted all parts of daily life across the various regions of England, including those areas which were not within the direct power bases of Stephen and Matilda in the south-east and the south-west. William of Malmesbury's *Historia Novella* expressed Stephen's own despair as the conflict was waging on throughout the kingdom (King, 2012:40-1)

'when they have elected me king, why do they abandon me? By the birth of God, I will never be called a king without a throne!'

While England's ruling elite certainly did gain more from the looser constraints of the twelfth-century, as the previous chapter affirmed, this assessment cannot be entirely justified. The only pitched battles of the period occurred at Northallerton in 1138 and in the city of Lincoln in 1141. Moreover, large portions of land in North Yorkshire were close to the Scottish borders and the security of this frontier was upheld by some of Stephen's most trusted and loyal supporters. This could only have been achieved if a degree of power and authority was still in place across the country. While he firmly believes that Stephen lost his ability to rule effectively, Edmund King noted how 'a failure of central control does not preclude the existence of effective control within the regions' (King, 1984:152). Instead, it has been argued by more recent historians that disputes and disagreements which defined the period were largely localised and in some cases, could simply represent the manifestations of local ambitions and political rivalries. An archaeological perspective of the relationship between these fortified monuments, including the practice of linking sites to local settlements and ecclesiastical sites, can help reveal the geo-spatial patterns between them and evaluate how geo-political factors could have influenced these landscapes while the war raged on.

1.3 Sources and Methods

Landscape studies surrounding secular and episcopal sites have since risen dramatically in recent years. The focus on Bodiam Castle's setting in the 1990s, has since led to other fortifications being reassessed and examined in new ways. Topography, access spatial analysis, and a study of the political context of these monuments, have revealed significantly more about them and this has led to a more holistic approach to be taken on the subject as a whole. While some individual sites have been studied in greater detail at castles such as Orford and Hedingham as a result, more work on sites constructed leading up to, during, and following the war between Stephen and Matilda's forces is needed. The work carried out by Oliver Creighton and Duncan Wright (2016) has done much to address this need in the south of England, but significant gaps remain in other areas. Due to their potential, 'individual local studies are, and will remain, the foundation of historical landscape enquiry' (Roberts, 2007:74). The regional approach of this chapter can take the subject into new realms of discovery and place its findings in a broader context.

The explosion in landscape studies has been met by an increase in the use of new methods and

technologies. One of the most valuable tools introduced to the field of archaeology has been the introduction of Geographical information systems. Despite its rise in popularity throughout the past two decades to archaeologists, it has been noted by some that ‘the growth in availability of GIS software has not always been accompanied by a corresponding increase in the knowledge and technical capabilities’ (Wheatley, 2002:1). It certainly has not been adopted by all tenets of castle studies and even fewer for those who have studied the fortifications used during the protracted struggle between King Stephen and the Empress Matilda. Owing to the fact that these structures have typically been studied from a historical perspective, and only as extensions of other arguments about challenges of the reign itself, the use of historical evidence has only taken the debate so far. GIS can provide an alternative way of assessing the historical and geo-spatial data and its use allows for a different view of Lincolnshire and Yorkshire’s development to be put forth.

Figure 1: Figure showing all known ‘fortified monuments’ built across Yorkshire and Lincolnshire during the eleventh and twelfth centuries.

1.4 Conclusions

Archaeologically, the twelfth century is largely a forgotten period and has typically been studied using primary accounts and government records. Benefiting from advances in research, excavation data and the use of GIS, a combined historical and archaeological approach can broaden the debate.

Lincolnshire and Yorkshire form the largest counties in England. In addition to their size, they are characterised by a diverse range of geographical features. While neighboured by several other counties, some of these characteristics are unique to this region and the terrain ranges from tall cliffs and hills across deep valleys, to low lying marshland in coastal areas. As well as the influence of the North Sea on the east of England, both counties contain a number of important rivers which dominated the

medieval landscape, and these may have affected the development of fortified buildings, as various pockets of land were reclaimed and adapted for human use. Taking this into account, the physical landscape must be considered if a greater picture of castle building during the eleventh and twelfth centuries is to be established. These locations, as well as the wealth of available resources they brought to them, would have provided significant possibilities for their occupants which would have far outstripped any other factor which led to their development at this pivotal moment in history. Lincolnshire and Yorkshire therefore provide an opportunity to assess the effects of Stephen and Matilda's rivalry and how it played out on the wider environment.

The distribution of 168 sites which forms the basis of this PhD research identified across the study area from the eleventh and twelfth centuries, can be seen in **Figure 1**. Unlike those built in stone, many timber castles or similar structures remain unknown to history and do not typically have visible remains. This makes their identification and interpretation difficult. The state of preservation has also inevitably strengthened the notions of anarchy as put forth by earlier historians that fortifications appeared as quickly as the disappeared in the landscape. Where excavation is not possible, it has been acknowledged that 'it is only by detailed survey, on the ground and from air photographs, that the precise character of a site can be demonstrated' (Higham, 2003:114). Many of these sites have become pastureland, or modern developments have skewed their original scopes which makes our interpretation of them all the more difficult. This has fuelled the assumptions made by chroniclers and traditional historians who argue that the England was gripped by large scale acts of war which left a lasting trace on its people and buildings. GIS can help reveal the locations and indeed siting of these buildings more effectively and in turn, better reveal how the builders of these fortifications were more concerned with local and political ambitions than were affected by the wider conflict between King Stephen and the Empress Matilda.

References:

Creighton, O. & Wright, D. (2016) *The Anarchy: War and Status in 12th Century Landscapes of Conflict*. Liverpool: Liverpool University Press.

Higham, R. (ed), (2003) *Chapter 5: Timber Castles: A Reassessment*. Woodbridge: The Boydell Press.

King, E. (1984) The Anarchy of King Stephen's Reign. *Transactions of the Royal Historical Society*, 34, 133-153.

King, E. (2012) *King Stephen*. New Haven and London: Yale University Press.

Roberts, B. K. (ed), (2007) *The Village: Contexts, Chronology and Causes.*, 2. BOLLINGTON: The Windgather Press LTD.

Wheatley, D. G., M. (2002) *Spatial Technology and Archaeology: The Archaeological Applications of GIS*. London: Taylor and Francis.

Biography:

Ryan Prescott is a PhD researcher in Archaeology based at the University of Hull and is interested in landscape studies of the medieval period, specifically the eleventh and twelfth centuries.